

DEFORMATION TEXTURE DEVELOPMENT IN A MODEL COMPOSITE SYSTEM

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ABSTRACT

Model composites fabricated with a polycrystalline copper matrix and continuous tungsten fibres were deformed in plane strain compression with the fibres perpendicular to the loading axis and parallel to the direction of zero strain. The development of texture in the matrix due to deformation was measured using x-ray diffraction. It was observed that the macroscopic texture development in the composite was weaker than for unreinforced copper. The pattern of deformation in the matrix was quantified using experimental measurements and finite element method calculations. By carefully sectioning the composite after deformation, texture measurements were conducted for regions which exhibited characteristic types of deformation. These measurements showed that there is a variety of local textures (some weaker, some stronger than the texture in the unreinforced matrix) which when summed give the result of a weak global texture. This result is in agreement with the predictions from the computer simulations of Bolmaro et al. [1].

INTRODUCTION

The development of deformation textures in the matrices of metal matrix composites (MMC's) has received relatively little attention. As Bunge [2] has pointed out, this may be due to the fact that state properties such as yield surfaces are less sensitive to matrix texture in two-phase materials compared to single phase materials. This is the case since anisotropy of mechanical properties in composites is typically dominated by anisotropy in the shape of the reinforcement. However, it has been generally observed that the development of deformation textures in the matrices of metal matrix composites is retarded in comparison with the base alloys [3-10]. It is important to understand the underlying deformation mechanisms which influence the local deformation textures in metal matrix composites since this may have important implications for the processing of these materials (for example, on their recrystallization behaviour).

Several different models have been made to explain these experimental results. These models are all based on a consideration of the effect of hard inclusions on the deformation of the matrix. These models have been reviewed by Bolmaro et al. [1] and can be summarized as follows:

1. Models which assume that the particle affects only the deformation of grains in the neighbourhood of the particle. These models are independent of the volume fraction of the reinforcement, and the effect of the inclusion is predicted to scale with the grain size of the material [11].
2. Dislocation models which predict rotations of the lattice adjacent to the particles as a result of dislocation accumulation and relaxation processes near the particles. In these models, effects of particles are largest adjacent to the particle and the magnitude of the effect increases as the a particle size decreases [6,7,10].
3. Models which assume the matrix behaves like a fluid and must flow around the particles. Here, the effects in the matrix may be largest midway between particles [1,4].

The present work was conducted in an attempt to provide experimental observations which would elucidate the important parameters that control the development of matrix texture in metal matrix composites.

EXPERIMENTAL

Model composites were fabricated using a liquid metal infiltration technique from copper (nominally 99.99 % purity) and commercially drawn tungsten fibres. The spacing and geometric arrangement of the tungsten fibres was controlled by holding the fibres in place with graphite spacers during fabrication. Composites with 20 and 30 % volume fraction tungsten were prepared with a triangular geometric arrangement of the fibres. The as-cast structure in the matrix was refined by a series of deformation and recrystallization processing steps (see Ref. 12 for complete details). Figure 1 illustrates a schematic diagram of a resulting composite and the starting microstructure. The matrix grain size was much smaller than the particle diameter (i.e. there were typically 5-10 copper grains between the fibres).

Figure 1 - a) schematic diagram of composite, b) optical micrograph of initial microstructure

The composites were deformed in plane strain compression using a channel die lubricated with a Teflon film and molybdisulphide spray. The composites were oriented so that the tungsten fibres were perpendicular to the loading axis and parallel to the direction of zero strain. Prior to

deformation a gold grid was prepared on the surface of the composite so that the local deformation conditions could be calculated based on a change in shape of the grid elements [12]. Experimental measurements of matrix texture ((111), (200) and (311) pole figures) were performed with a Scintag texture goniometer using $\text{CuK}\alpha$ radiation. The resulting experimental pole figures were processed with the popLA software package [13] to produce fully normalized, complete pole figures. Measurements were performed on the face of the composite sample perpendicular the fibre axis and on sectioned faces of the sample parallel to the fibre axis shown in Figure 2. Note that all pole figures shown in this work are oriented so that the centre of the pole figure corresponds to the transverse direction (typical pole figures from plane strain deformation are oriented so that the normal direction lies at the centre of the pole figures)

Figure 2 - Schematic diagram illustrating sectioning

EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS

The initial matrix textures for the 20 % and 30 % volume fraction samples are shown in Figures 3a and 4a respectively. The initial textures have some deviations from a random texture connected with the relatively large initial grain size (50-200 μm). However, there is no evidence of specific initial texture components. The textures after deformation (imposed strain of 0.2 for the 30 % sample and 0.3 for 20 % sample) are shown in Figures 3b and 4b. The matrix texture in the 20 % volume fraction sample (i.e. Figure 3b) after deformation illustrates some features of plane strain deformation texture. Specifically the presence of higher than average intensities at orientations marked "A" and "B" and the low intensities at the orientations "C" and "D". However, the texture is at a much weaker level than would be expected for the unreinforced material. The 30 % volume fraction sample shows an even weaker level of texture development than the 20 % volume fraction sample (see Figure 4b).

DISCUSSION

The present result indicating relatively weak deformation textures in the composite is in agreement with results of other workers [3-10]. In order to discuss the results for texture development in the composites it is useful to consider the pattern of deformation in the matrix. The deformation pattern of the matrix is affected by the spacing and geometric arrangement of the second phase. The pattern of deformation was predicted using finite element method (FEM) calculations. This is illustrated in Figure 5 which shows the change in shape of an initially square grid after an imposed deformation of 0.35. The predictions from the FEM calculations have been qualitatively and quantitatively validated from experimental measurements of local strain (i.e. from the change in shape of the initially square gold grid [12]). The experiments and

Figure 3 - (111) pole figures for 20 % volume fraction composite, a) initial undeformed (experimental), b) after deformation to a strain of 0.3 (experimental) and c) predicted deformation texture from Bolmaro et al. [1].

Figure 4 - Experimentally determined (111) pole figures for 30 % volume fraction, a) initial and b) after deformation to a strain 0.3.

calculations show that the local level of strain varies spatially. The variations occur at two levels:

1. there are effects local to the fibres which have mostly disappeared at distances equal to $1/4$ the fibre diameter into the matrix (these effects are observed even in the case of single fibre experiments [14],
2. there are effects which occur midway between the fibres. These effects have been found to depend strongly on the spacing and geometric arrangement of the fibres. (A complete description of the deformation patterns is given in [12].)

Figure 5 - Finite element method calculated predictions for the deformation pattern in 20 % volume fraction sample after imposed deformation of 0.35.

In the work of Bolmaro et al. [1], it was proposed that the variations away from the fibres would dominate the global texture development since these regions occupy a much larger volume proportion of the matrix than the material near the fibres. In particular, they predicted that for the triangular arrangement of fibres, there would be two main characteristic regions (i.e. regions with a characteristic strain path history). The representative regions (shown in Figure 5) have deformation behaviour characteristic of i) pure shear (i.e. on the horizontal between fibres) and ii) simple shear (i.e. on the diagonal between fibres), although this region is further complicated by a changing strain path during deformation. Bolmaro and Kocks [15] have shown that much weaker deformation textures are expected for simple shear deformation when compared to pure shear deformation. Furthermore, the additional effect of a varying strain path during deformation would be expected to further weaken the deformation texture for the regions along the diagonals between the fibres. Bolmaro et al. [1] accounted for the varying strain path during deformation by using the predicted strain path history from the FEM calculations as an input to the texture simulation code [16]. Their predictions for the local textures in the representative regions are shown in Figure 6a and 6b (for a point midway along the horizontal axis between the fibres and a point midway along the diagonal axis between the fibres, respectively). Finally, Bolmaro et al.

Figure 6 - (111) pole figures for 20 % volume fraction composite after deformation to a strain of 0.3, a) sectioned along horizontal axis (experimental), b) sectioned along diagonal axis (experimental), c) predicted deformation texture for a point along horizontal axis between fibres, and d) predicted deformation texture for a point along diagonal axis between fibres; from Bolmaro et al. [1].

made the assumption that a simple addition of these local texture components would give an average value for the global deformation texture (i.e. such as would be experimentally measured). The prediction of Bolmaro et al. is shown in Figure 5c which can be directly compared to the experimental measurement in Figure 5b. There is qualitative agreement between the main features in the experimental and predicted textures although the predicted textures are sharper and stronger. However, it is generally observed that predicted textures are stronger than experimental textures using this type of texture models [17].

In order to further investigate the predictions of Bolmaro et al., the experimental samples were sectioned as shown in Figure 2 so that texture measurements could be made from the representative regions. The results of these experiments are shown in Figure 6c and 6d. Once again, the qualitative features of the experimental and predicted textures (Figure 6a and 6b) are in agreement. It is important to point out that the local textures may be weaker or stronger than the textures expected in the unreinforced material. For example, the texture in the region on the horizontal axis between the fibres experiences a much a larger strain than the macroscopically imposed deformation and hence has a stronger texture. It is, however, the averaging of the local textures which leads to the observation of weak global texture development.

Finally, careful observation of Figure 6d indicates that there is a cube texture component. Cube texture components in FCC materials are associated with recrystallization textures. It is therefore likely that this texture component formed during the prior deformation and recrystallization processing which was used to refine the matrix grain size. However, it is interesting that the cube component was only found in the section through the diagonal axis of fibres (which had the "simple shear" type of deformation during prior processing). The effect of strain path on recrystallization textures is an area that requires further investigation.

CONCLUSIONS

1. The present work is in agreement with previous results in that the observed deformation textures in the composites are weaker than in the unreinforced matrix.
2. The experimental evidence from this work supports the predictions of Bolmaro et al. that global deformation texture is weakened due to a superposition of local deformation textures. It is the averaging of local texture components which leads to the weaker observed global textures.
3. The local textures may be stronger or weaker than the deformation texture in the unreinforced matrix for a similar level of strain depending on the local pattern of deformation in the matrix.
4. The deformation texture is dominated by effects in the regions between the fibres as opposed to the material adjacent to the fibres.

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